

Cut out and glue the pieces, and you're ready to play!

Biomarkers

Dice

Cut out and glue the pieces, and you're ready to play!

Counters

Biosensor

Cut out and glue the pieces, and you're ready to play!

Tokens

AQLUA

Players' names

Player 1	Player 2	Player 3	Player 4
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WHO?					
	White-legged Shrimp				
	Sea bass				
	Atlantic salmon				
	Rainbow Trout				

WHY?

	Fish net				
	Disease				
	Increase in water temperature				
	Pollution				
	Low salinity				
	Transportation				
	High density				
	Low oxygen				
	Poor water quality				

HOW TO DETECT?

	Water				
	Skin mucus				
	Blood				
	Scales				
	Plasma				
	Behaviour				
	Faeces				

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